

INDEPENDENT WORK: PREPARATION AND TYPES

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ABSTRACT

By the beginning of their studies at the university, each student has personal experience and skills in organizing their own actions, acquired in the process of studying at school, institutions of additional education, during extracurricular activities and at home. However, when studying at a university, the requirements for organizing independent work increase significantly, since they are associated with the development of complex general cultural and professional competencies.

Keywords: educational process, methodological guidance, competencies, thinking, content, self-development, notes.

ANNOTATSIYA

Universitetda o'qish boshlanishiga qadar har bir talaba maktabda, qo'shimcha ta'lim muassasalarida, darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda va uyda o'qish paytida olingan shaxsiy harakatlarini tashkil qilish bo'yicha shaxsiy tajriba va ko'nikmalarga ega. Biroq, universitetda o'qiyotganda, mustaqil ishni tashkil etish talablari sezilarli darajada oshadi, chunki ular murakkab umumiy madaniy va kasbiy vakolatlarni rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim jarayoni, uslubiy rahbarlik, kompetensiyalar, fikrlash, mazmun, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish, eslatmalar

АННОТАЦИЯ

К началу обучения в вузе каждый студент обладает личным опытом и навыками организации собственных действий, приобретенными в процессе обучения в школе, учреждениях дополнительного образования, во время внеклассной деятельности и дома. Однако при обучении в вузе требования к организации самостоятельной работы существенно возрастают, поскольку они связаны с развитием сложных общекультурных и профессиональных компетенций.

Ключевые слова: образовательный процесс, методическое руководство, компетенции, мышление, содержание, саморазвитие, заметки.

According to the requirements of regulatory documents, independent work of students is an obligatory component of the educational process, as it ensures the consolidation of knowledge gained in the classroom by acquiring skills to comprehend and expand the knowledge itself, skills to solve urgent problems of formation of general cultural and professional competencies, research activities, preparation for seminars, laboratory work, passing tests and exams.

The independent work of students is a planned educational or research work of students, which is carried out during extracurricular time on the initiative of the student or an assignment of a teacher, and with the methodical guidance of the teacher or without his direct participation.

Independent work of students is a combination of classroom and extracurricular activities and assignments that ensure the successful development of an educational program in accordance with educational standards. The skills of independent work on mastering any knowledge are acquired by a person from early childhood and develop throughout the life. By the beginning of their studies at the university, each student has personal experience and skills in organizing their own actions, acquired in the process of studying at school, institutions of additional education, during extracurricular activities and at home. However, when studying at a university, the requirements for organizing independent work increase significantly, since they are associated with the development of complex general cultural and professional competencies. Practice shows that students differ in their level of readiness to implement the requirements for independent work.

There are two main groups of students:

- The first one is characterized by the fact that its representatives are focused on completing tasks of independent work and have universal educational competencies that allow them to successfully cope with the requirements for its implementation (the ability to understand and memorize acquired information, think logically, reproduce material in writing and orally, carry out measurements, calculations, design, etc.).

- Students of the second group do not have a stable orientation to constantly perform independent work while mastering educational material and are characterized by a low level of development of universal educational competencies and self-organization skills.

Independent work within the framework of the educational process at a university solves the following tasks:

- consolidation and expansion of knowledge and skills acquired by students during classroom and extracurricular activities, turning them into stereotypes of mental and physical activity;
- acquisition of additional knowledge and skills in the disciplines of the curriculum;

- formation and development of knowledge and skills related to research activities;
- development of orientation and attitude towards high-quality mastery of the educational program;
- development of self-organization skills;
- formation of independent thinking, ability for self-development, self-improvement and self-realization;
- development of skills for effective independent professional theoretical, practical and educational and research activities.

To fulfill the tasks of students' independent work and its implementation, a number of conditions are required that are provided by the university:

- availability of material and technical base;
- availability of the necessary fund of information for students' independent work and the ability to work with it in classroom and out of class time;
- availability of premises for performing specific tasks included in students' independent work;
- validity of the content of tasks included in students' independent work;
- connection between independent work and syllabus, calculation of the required time for independent work;
- development by teachers of students' self-organization skills and universal educational competencies;
- at all stages of students' independent work there should be support by teachers, ongoing and final monitoring of its results.

The specific principles of organization and independent work within the framework of the modern educational process are:

- the principle of interactive learning (providing interactive dialogue and feedback, which allows the control and correction of student actions);
- the principle of developing the student's intellectual potential (formation of algorithmic, visual-figurative, theoretical styles of thinking, skills to make optimal or variable decisions in a difficult situation, skills to process information);
- the principle of ensuring the integrity and continuity of the didactic training cycle (providing the opportunity to complete all parts of the didactic cycle within the topic, section, module).

Independent work of students is planned by each teacher in the work program of the discipline, and its credit types are recorded in the technological map, in which students can

always find information about the amount of independent work, the time of their completion and the maximum score when assessing the results of their implementation. The amount of time allocated for extracurricular independent work is reflected: in the curriculum as a whole for theoretical training, for each cycle of disciplines, for each discipline; in the work programs of academic disciplines with an approximate distribution by sections or specific topics. Independent work of students is classified: by place of organization (classroom and extracurricular); according to the goals of the organization (the goals of the discipline formulated and justified in the work program); by method of organization (individual, group). The choice of the form of organizing students' independent work (individual or group) is determined by the content of the academic discipline and the form of organization of training (lecture, seminar, practical lesson, control lesson, etc.). Depending on the form of intermediate certification, types of independent work are supplemented by preparation for the exam, test and current certification procedures.

Below there are different levels of independent work:

1. Independent work according to the model is a low level of independence. They require the transfer of a known method of solution directly to a similar or remotely similar intra-subject situation. These works are performed on the basis of “specific algorithms” previously demonstrated by the teacher and tested by students during previous assignments. Thus, by performing independent work of this type, students make a direct transfer of a known method to a similar intra-subject situation

2. Independent work of a reconstructive-variative type is a threshold level of independence. They allow you to meaningfully transfer knowledge into typical situations, teach you to analyze events, phenomena, facts, create conditions for the development of students' mental activity, and form techniques and methods of cognitive activity

3. Heuristic independent work is an advanced level of independence. Contribute to the formation of the creative personality of students. When performing work of this type, there is a constant search for new solutions, generalization and systematization of acquired knowledge, and transfer of them to completely non-standard situations.

4. Intra-subject and inter-subject independent research work is a high level of independence. This is the highest level in the system of independent work. To carry out such independent work, you must be able to transform and transfer knowledge and methods of solving problems, independently develop new methods of solution, determine the content, purpose, and develop a plan for solving an educational problem. Independent work of this type usually contains cognitive tasks, the conditions of which require: analyze unusual situations; identify characteristic signs of learning problems that arise in these situations; look for ways to solve

these problems; choose the most rational ones from the known methods, modifying them in accordance with the conditions of the learning situation.

To effectively perform independent work at different levels, a student needs to possess a stable set of methods of activity to solve various types of educational tasks. First of all, we are talking about the ability to take notes, select examples, compare, establish interdisciplinary connections, use additional literature, paraphrase, draw up a conceptual tree, etc. Particular attention should be paid to metacognitive methods of activity that contribute to the formation of general cultural and professional competencies and ensure the development of self-organization and self-control of educational activities. They are as follows:

- planning (drawing up a plan, building the logic of content, setting a goal, implementing a goal, etc.);
- observation (assessing what has been achieved, answering questions for self-control, applying theory in practice, writing abstracts on a topic, referring to other scientific sources, etc.);
- regulation (self-esteem, use of additional resources, volitional regulation, a certain sequence of task completion, etc.)

The main types of classroom activities at a university are lecture, practical lesson, seminar, seminar-conference, colloquium, and within the framework of control activities - test, test, exam.

Let's take a closer look at the features of self-preparation for classroom lessons of these types.

Preparation for practical training. Preparation for a practical lesson includes the following elements of independent activity: a clear idea of the purpose and objectives of its implementation; highlighting the skills of mental, analytical, scientific activity that will become the result of the upcoming work. The development of skills is carried out through obtaining new information about the processes being studied and through knowledge of the extent to which the student currently owns research methods that he will use in a practical lesson.

Consequently, work in a practical lesson is aimed not only at the student's knowledge of specific phenomena of the external world, but also at changing himself. The second result is very important, since it ensures the formation of such general cultural competencies as the ability for self-organization and self-education, the ability to use methods of collecting, processing and interpreting complex information to solve organizational and managerial problems, including those outside the student's immediate sphere of activity. Preparation for a practical lesson often requires the selection of material, data and special sources with which the educational work will

be carried out. Students should prepare at home for class 3–4 examples of the formulation of a research topic presented in monographs, scientific articles, reports.

Preparation for the seminar-conference. The seminar-conference is held 1–3 times a semester, as it involves quite a long period of independent training for students studying a specific scientific problem. It combines activities corresponding to a regular seminar session and a scientific conference, which provides for an organized discussion of reports from different researchers on a certain range of problems. In the process of independent preparation for the seminar-conference, the student needs to study 2-3 sources (monographs, articles), which reveal theoretical approaches to the issue under discussion and present empirical research materials. The speaker must be prepared to answer questions from everyone present on the topic of his report. After each presentation there is a discussion of the presented scientific views of different researchers. Readiness for such analytical collective work is ensured by each student viewing the main works that the teacher recommended reading for the seminar-conference.

Preparation for the colloquium. A colloquium is a collective discussion of a section of a discipline based on independent study of this section by students. Preparation for this type of training is carried out in the following order. The teacher gives a list of questions, the answers to which should be obtained by studying a certain list of scientific sources. During extracurricular time, students need to read specialized literature, write down answers to questions that will be discussed at the colloquium, and mentally formulate their opinion on each of the questions that they will express in class.

Preparation for the test. The test is assigned after studying a certain section (sections) of the discipline and is a set of detailed written answers from students to questions that they receive in advance from the teacher. Independent preparation for the test includes:

- studying lecture notes that cover the material, the knowledge of which is tested by the test;
- repetition of educational material received in preparation for seminars, practical classes and during their implementation;
- study of additional literature, which specifies the content of the knowledge being tested;
- composing in mental form answers to the questions posed in the test;
- formation of a psychological attitude towards the successful completion of all tasks.

Preparation for tests (including differentiated tests in the absence of an exam in the discipline). The test is a traditional form of testing the knowledge, skills, and competencies developed by students in the process of mastering the entire content of the discipline being

studied. A regular test differs from an exam only in that the teacher does not differentiate the points he assigns based on its results. In the case of a differentiated test, the student receives points that reflect the level of his knowledge, but they are not indicated in the grade book: only the word “test” is written in it. Independent preparation for the test should be carried out throughout the semester, and not a few days before it takes place. Preparation includes the following steps. First of all, you need to re-read all the lectures, as well as the materials that were prepared for seminars and practical classes during the semester. Then you need to correlate this information with the questions that are given for testing. If there is not enough information, answers are found in the literature suggested by the teacher. It is recommended to take brief notes. This is not about a cheat sheet, but about the formation in the mind of a clear logical scheme for answering a question. On the eve of the test, you must repeat the answers without looking at the notes.

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